

LINGUOCULTURAL ASPECTS OF LANGUAGE TEACHING IN A MULTICULTURAL ENVIRONMENT

Raikan Apzhaparovna Ysmailova

Associate professor, Candidate of Philosophical Sciences,
Department of English Phonetics and Grammar, Institute of Philology and
Intercultural Communication, Osh State University,
rismailova@oshsu.kg

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0220-2605>

Adylbekova Bekzada Uzakbaevna

Senior lecturer of Department of Social-Humanitarian disciplines, International
Medical Faculty, Osh State University,
badylbekova@oshsu.kg

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1460-015X>

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Annotation. The article examines the linguocultural aspects of teaching languages in a multicultural educational environment formed as a result of globalization and migration processes. It analyzes the close relationship between language and culture, emphasizing the role of language as a fundamental carrier of cultural information and values. The study focuses on the functional features of the multicultural space and its impact on the cognitive development of students.

The paper offers practical recommendations for educators on developing educational materials adapted to the needs of a diverse audience. Particular attention is paid to methods for developing intercultural communicative competence and overcoming linguistic and cultural barriers. The author substantiates the effectiveness of using the comparative-typological method and modern information and communication technologies in the learning process. The article highlights the necessity of integrating a cultural component into language training for the successful social adaptation of students in the modern world.

Keywords: Linguocultural studies, multicultural environment, language teaching, intercultural communication, cultural competence, language competence, authentic materials, information and communication technologies, comparative method, globalization, migration.

Аннотация. Бул мақалада глобалдашуу жана миграциялык процесстердин натыйжасында калыптанган көп маданияттуу билим берүү чөйрөсүндө тилдерди окутуунун лингвокультурологиялык аспекти лери каралат. Автор тил менен маданияттын ортосундагы тыгыз байланышты талдап, тилдин маданий маалыматтарды жана баалуулуктарды алып жүрүүчү негизги курал катары ролун баса белгилейт. Изилдөө көп маданияттуу мейкиндиктин өзгөчөлүктөрүнө жана анын студенттердин когнитивдик өнүгүүсүнө тийгизген таасирине багытталган.

Иш алкагында мугалимдер үчүн көп улуттуу аудиториянын муктаждыктарына ылайыкташтырылган окуу материалдарын иштеп чыгуу боюнча практикалык сунуштар берилген. Маданияттар аралык коммуникативдик компетенттүүлүктү калыптандырууга, тилдик жана маданий тоскоолдуктарды жеңүүгө өзгөчө көңүл бурулат. Автор окуу процессинде салыштырма-типологиялык методду жана заманбап маалыматтык-коммуникациялык технологияларды колдонуунун натыйжалуулугун негиздейт. Макала студенттердин заманбап дүйнөдө ийгиликтүү социалдык адаптациясы үчүн тилдик даярдыкка маданий компонентти интеграциялоо зарылдыгын көрсөтөт.

Ачкыч сөздөр: лингвокультурология, көп маданияттуу чөйрө, тил окутуу, маданияттар аралык коммуникация, маданий компетенттүүлүк, тилдик компетенттүүлүк, түп нуска (аутентикалык) материалдар, маалыматтык-коммуникациялык технологиялар, салыштырмалуу метод, глобалдашуу, миграция.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются лингвокультурологические аспекты преподавания языков в поликультурной образовательной среде, сформированной под влиянием глобализации и миграционных процессов. Автор анализирует тесную взаимосвязь языка и культуры, подчеркивая роль языка как фундаментального носителя культурной информации и ценностей. Исследование фокусируется на особенностях функционирования мультикультурного пространства и его влияния на когнитивное развитие учащихся.

В работе предложены практические рекомендации для педагогов по созданию учебных материалов, адаптированных к потребностям многонациональной аудитории. Особое внимание уделяется методам формирования межкультурной коммуникативной компетенции, преодолению языковых и культурных барьеров. Автор обосновывает эффективность применения сравнительно-типологического метода и современных информационно-коммуникационных технологий в учебном процессе. Статья подчеркивает необходимость интеграции культурного компонента в языковую подготовку для успешной социальной адаптации студентов в современном мире.

Ключевые слова: лингвокультурология, поликультурная среда, преподавание языков, межкультурная коммуникация, культурная компетенция, языковая компетенция, аутентичные материалы, информационно-коммуникационные технологии, сравнительный метод, глобализация, миграция.

Introduction

The modern world is characterized by the steady growth of globalization and migration processes, which leads to the formation of a multicultural environment in educational institutions. In these conditions, traditional approaches to teaching languages are insufficient, since they do not take into account the linguacultural aspects that play a key role in successful intercultural communication. Linguacultural studies, as a science that studies the relationship between language and culture, provides the necessary theoretical and methodological basis for developing effective methods of teaching languages in a multicultural environment. It allows us to understand how cultural characteristics influence the perception and use of language, as well as how language, in turn, shapes cultural ideas.

This article examines the linguacultural aspects of teaching languages in a multicultural environment, analyzes key concepts such as “linguacultural studies” and “multicultural environment”, defines the purpose and objectives of the study, and offers methodological recommendations for taking into account linguacultural aspects in the process of teaching languages. The relationship between language and culture is fundamental to linguacultural studies. Language is not just a means of communication, but also an instrument that shapes and reflects culture. As V.V. Vorobyev notes, “language and culture are two sides of the same coin, inextricably linked and interpenetrating each other.” (Vorobyev, 1997, p.331). Language reflects the cultural values, traditions and worldview of the people. Cultural concepts, stereotypes and symbols are transmitted through language. Studying a language without taking into account its cultural context does not allow us to fully understand its meaning and use.

Language acts as the main carrier of cultural information. It preserves and transmits the historical experience, traditions, customs and values of the people. As Yu. S. Stepanov writes, "language is not just a means of communication, but also a means of preserving and transmitting culture." (Stepanov, 2001, p.798). Through language, we learn about the cultural characteristics of the people, their history, religion, art and literature. Language shapes our worldview and influences our behavior.

The linguacultural approach to teaching languages assumes taking into account the cultural context of the language being studied. It is aimed at developing intercultural competence in students, which is necessary for successful communication with representatives of other cultures. V.V. Krasnykh notes that "the linguacultural approach assumes the integration of linguistic and cultural components in the learning process" (Krasnykh, 2002, p.37). This approach includes the study of cultural concepts, stereotypes, and symbols reflected in the language. It also assumes familiarization with the cultural traditions, customs, and norms of behavior of native speakers of the language being studied.

A multicultural educational environment is characterized by a diversity of cultural values, traditions, and norms of behavior. This creates both opportunities and challenges for teaching languages. G.I. Gaysina emphasizes that "a multicultural educational environment requires teachers to take into account the cultural characteristics of students and create conditions for intercultural dialogue" (Gaysina, 2011, p.13-17.). The teacher must be prepared to work with students with different cultural and linguistic backgrounds. He must be able to create an atmosphere of tolerance and respect for cultural differences.

In a multicultural educational environment, where representatives of different cultures and languages coexist, traditional teaching methods often prove insufficient. Effective teaching requires the use of interactive methods that promote intercultural dialogue and exchange of experience. As S.G. Ter-Minasova notes: "Teaching a foreign language is always a dialogue of cultures, and this dialogue should be active, lively, interactive." (Ter-Minasova, 2000, 458)

Interactive methods such as discussions, role-playing games, projects and case studies enable learners to actively participate in the learning process, exchange opinions and experiences, and develop intercultural communication skills. They help develop learners' ability to empathize, tolerate and respect cultural differences.

In addition, in a multicultural educational environment, it is extremely important to use authentic materials that reflect the cultural characteristics of the language being studied. According to I. I. Khaleeva, "authentic materials are not only a source of linguistic information, but also a means of immersion in the culture of the language being studied." (Khaleeva, 2000, p.387, 396)

Authentic materials such as films, songs, articles, interviews and literary works allow learners to become familiar with the real language and culture of native speakers. They help develop learners' linguistic and cultural competencies necessary for successful intercultural communication.

The use of authentic materials in combination with interactive teaching methods allows us to create an atmosphere of intercultural dialogue and exchange of experience in a multicultural educational environment, which contributes to effective language learning and the development of intercultural competence in students.

Teaching methods and techniques that take into account linguistic and cultural features. Teaching languages in a multicultural environment requires flexibility and creativity from the teacher. It is necessary to use methods and techniques that take into

account the linguistic and cultural characteristics of the students. Interactive methods, such as discussions and debates on topics related to the culture of the target language and the cultures of the students, promote active involvement of students in the learning process (Elizarova, 2005). Role-playing games and simulations that model situations of intercultural communication allow students to practice communication skills in realistic conditions. Project activities aimed at studying the cultural characteristics of the countries of the target language develop students' research skills and broaden their horizons. For example, organizing a discussion on the topic of "Cultural Differences in Understanding the Concept of Time" with the participation of representatives of different cultures allows students to better understand how cultural factors affect the perception of time.

The use of authentic materials, such as films, songs, literary works reflecting the culture of the target language, helps students immerse themselves in the linguistic and cultural environment. Media articles and interviews about cultural events and phenomena allow students to learn about current events and trends in the target language countries. Using online resources such as podcasts, blogs, and social media allows students to interact with native speakers of the target language and learn about their culture. For example, analyzing excerpts from literary works to identify cultural concepts and stereotypes allows students to gain a deeper understanding of the cultural characteristics of target language countries.

Teaching materials used in a multicultural environment should be carefully tailored to the needs of learners with diverse cultural and linguistic backgrounds. A key aspect is the inclusion of culture-specific materials that help students better understand the culture of the target language. This may include texts and activities that introduce cultural traditions, customs and norms of behavior of native speakers, as well as illustrations and photographs that reflect the cultural characteristics of the countries where the target language is spoken. For example, developing a teaching module devoted to exploring the cultural characteristics of New Year celebrations in different countries can be an effective way to introduce students to cultural diversity.

In addition, using a comparative-contrastive approach allows students to better understand the cultural differences and similarities between the target language and their native language. This involves comparing the cultural concepts and stereotypes of the target language with the cultural concepts and stereotypes of the learners' native language, as well as analyzing differences in language norms and speech behavior. For example, comparing phraseological units reflecting the concept of "home" in different cultures can help students understand how cultural values influence language.

The development of intercultural communicative competence is one of the key tasks of teaching languages in a multicultural environment. This involves not only the development of language skills, but also the development of the ability to effectively interact with representatives of other cultures. The development of language competencies includes teaching vocabulary and grammar necessary for communication in various situations of intercultural interaction, as well as the development of listening, reading, writing and speaking skills. However, in addition to language skills, it is necessary to develop sociocultural competencies, which include teaching cultural norms and rules of behavior in the countries of the studied language, as well as the development of empathy, tolerance and respect for cultural differences. For example, organizing trainings to develop intercultural communication skills, including the analysis of conflict situations and the search for ways to resolve them, helps students learn to effectively interact with representatives of other cultures.

The use of information and communication technologies in the process of teaching languages in a multicultural environment significantly enrich language learning in a multicultural environment. Using online resources such as electronic dictionaries and social networks helps students to get acquainted with the authentic language and communicate with native speakers. Multimedia materials such as video and audio create an immersive language and cultural environment. For example, virtual excursions allow students to explore the culture of the countries of the language they are learning.

The comparative-contrastive method is a powerful tool that allows learners to gain a deeper understanding of the cultural characteristics of the language being studied through comparison with their native culture (Safonova, 1991). This method includes two main areas: comparison of linguistic phenomena and comparison of cultural concepts. Comparison of linguistic phenomena involves the analysis of grammatical constructions, lexical units and phraseological units, as well as differences in speech behavior and communication strategies. For example, an analysis of how politeness is expressed in different languages. Comparison of cultural concepts includes an analysis of cultural values, traditions, norms of behavior, worldview and mentality. For example, a comparison of the concepts of "hospitality" and "friendship" in Russian and Chinese cultures allows us to identify differences in the understanding of these concepts and their linguistic expression. This approach helps develop intercultural competence in learners and helps them avoid cultural misunderstandings.

Teaching languages in a multicultural environment plays a key role in developing intercultural competence and intercultural dialogue. It helps students develop empathy, tolerance and respect for cultural differences, as well as intercultural communication and cooperation skills. In addition, teaching languages in a multicultural environment helps develop global citizenship by instilling in students a sense of responsibility for preserving cultural diversity and peace on the planet, as well as developing skills for intercultural interaction and cooperation on a global scale.

The prospects for teaching languages in a multicultural environment are associated with the further development of linguacultural studies, the development of innovative teaching methods and techniques, as well as the use of information and communication technologies to create an interactive and exciting educational environment. It is important that teaching is not only effective, but also interesting, motivating students to study languages and cultures.

Analysis of the experience of teaching languages in a multicultural environment is an important stage in the development of effective teaching methods and techniques. A review of existing methods and practices allows us to identify the most successful approaches and determine areas requiring further development. For example, an analysis of the experience of teaching English in international schools shows that the use of a communicative approach in combination with project activities and authentic materials helps to develop students' not only linguistic but also socio-cultural competencies. However, an analysis of unsuccessful examples, such as ignoring cultural differences and using outdated methods, shows that this leads to a decrease in students' motivation and complicates the learning process. Typical mistakes and problems identified in the analysis include: insufficient training of teachers to work in a multicultural environment, lack of adapted teaching materials, ignoring the individual needs of students, and insufficient use of ICT.

Conclusions

The conducted research showed that teaching languages in a multicultural environment requires a special approach that takes into account the linguacultural characteristics of students. The use of interactive methods, authentic materials, a comparative approach and

ICT allows creating an effective educational environment that promotes the formation of intercultural communicative competence.

Effective language teaching in a multicultural environment requires teachers and educational institutions to take a comprehensive approach, including the development of intercultural competence, the use of diverse teaching methods, the adaptation of teaching materials, the creation of a tolerant environment and the active use of ICT.

Development of practical recommendations for teachers and educational institutions:

For teachers:

-Develop your intercultural competence and knowledge of the cultural characteristics of students.

-Use a variety of methods and techniques that take into account linguistic and cultural characteristics.

-Adapt teaching materials to the needs of learners with different cultural and linguistic backgrounds.

-Create an atmosphere of tolerance and respect for cultural differences.

-Use ICT to create an interactive and engaging learning environment.

For educational institutions:

-Organize advanced training courses for teachers on issues of teaching languages in a multicultural environment.

-Develop and implement educational programs oriented towards a multicultural environment.

-To create conditions for intercultural dialogue and exchange of experience between students.

-Provide access to ICT and other necessary resources.

Prospects for further research in this area are related to the study of the influence of new technologies on the process of teaching languages in a multicultural environment, the development of innovative teaching methods and techniques, as well as the study of the role of linguacultural aspects in the formation of global citizenship.

Literature:

1. Elizarova, G. V. (2005), Culture and teaching foreign languages. — St. Petersburg: KARO.
2. Gaysina, G. I. (2011), Multicultural education as a factor in the socialization of the individual // Bulletin of the Bashkir State Pedagogical University named after M. Akmulla. — No. 4. — P. 13-17.
3. Khaleeva, I. I. (2000), Secondary linguistic personality as a recipient of a foreign-language text // Language. System. Personality: Collection of scientific papers for the 70th anniversary of Professor K.G. Krasnykh. — M.: Moscow State Linguistic University, P. 216-224.
4. Krasnykh, V. V. (2002), Ethnopsycholinguistics and linguacultural studies: a course of lectures. — M.: Gnosis, 284 p.
5. Safonova, V. V. (1991), Sociocultural approach to teaching foreign languages. — M.: Higher School.
6. Stepanov, Yu. S. (2001), Constants: dictionary of Russian culture. — M.: Academic project, 990 p.
7. Ter-Minasova, S. G. (2000), Language and intercultural communication. — M.: Slovo/Slovo, 624 p.

8. Vorobyev, V. V. (1997), *Linguoculturology: theory and methods*. — M.: ITDGK "Gnosis", 331 p.